

Macrocyclic nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of the deca- and tetradecaaza ligands

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Abstract : Template condensation reactions between the dinuclear nickel(II) or copper(II) complexes of the hexaaza macrocycles 1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaaza-8,8,16,16-tetrachlorocyclohexadecane (HTCH) or 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclooctadecane (HTCO) and triethylenetetramine have yielded products of three new macrocyclic ring systems : 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,20,23,26,29,30,33,36-tetradecaazadispiro[10.7.10.7]hexatriacontane (TDSH), 2,5,8,11,14,17,19,22,25,28-decaaza-9,10-dichlorobicyclo[16.10.0]octacosane (DDCO) and 2,5,8,10,13,16,19,21,24,27,29,32,35,38-tetradecaazatricyclo[26.10.0.0^{9,20}]octatriacontane (TTCO). Formulation of these products as $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{TDSH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{10}]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{TDSH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_8$, $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DDCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\text{Cl}_6$ and $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{TTCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{10}]\text{Cl}_8$ and the metal-free TDSH.14HCl has been supported by elemental analyses, conductivity measurements, melting points and spectroscopic studies.

Keywords : Copper(II), nickel(II), macrocyclic, ligand.

Introduction

A number of dinuclear complexes of macrocycles incorporating metals within a large ring or in two separate rings connected by a bridge(s) have been synthesized in view of their unusual electronic and chemical properties¹. Recently, we studied dinuclear nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of the hexaazamacrocycles 1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaaza-8,8,16,16-tetrachlorocyclohexadecane (HTCH) and 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclooctadecane (HTCO) generated by the template condensation of triethylenetetramine with carbon tetrachloride and 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane, respectively^{2,3}. In the present work, some new ring systems have been derived from the complexes of HTCH and HTCO. Triethylenetetramine condensed with $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{HTCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the presence of the corresponding metal hydroxide to form tetrametallic complexes of the macrocyclic ligand 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,20,23,26,29,30,33,36-tetradecaazadispiro[10.7.10.7]hexatriacontane (TDSH). But, condensation of triethylenetetramine with $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4$ complex yielded two products, trimetallic and tetrametallic complexes of the macrocycles 2,5,8,11,14,17,19,22,25,28-decaaza-9,10-dichlorobicyclo[16.10.0]octacosane (DDCO) and 2,5,8,10,13,

16,19,21,24,27,29,32,35,38-tetradecaazatricyclo[26.10.0.0^{9,20}]octatriacontane (TTCO), respectively. The structures of the macrocycles are shown in Fig. 1.

Experimental

Materials :

Reagent grade chemicals were used in the synthesis of the macrocyclic nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes.

Measurements :

Using KBr pellets infrared spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer model 387 spectrophotometer in the range 4000–250 cm^{-1} . Solution conductivity measurements were performed with a DDR conductivity meter (type 304)⁴. ¹H NMR spectra were run on a Bruker DRX 300 (300 MHz FT) in D₂O solution using DSS as an internal standard. Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were determined at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, and the ionizable chloride ions were analyzed by conductometric titrations. Nickel(II) and copper(II) contents in the complexes were determined by EDTA titration⁵ after decomposition of the complexes⁴. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX 102/DA-600 spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 100 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature. *m*-Nitrobenzyl alcohol was used as the matrix.

Fig. 1. Suggested structure of the ligands.

Synthesis of the nickel(II) complex of 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,20,23,26,29,30,33,36-tetradecaazadispiro[10.7.10.7]hexatriacontane (TDSH) :

$[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4$ was prepared in solution by heating equimolar amounts of nickel hydroxide (3.00 g, 32.35 mmol), diethylenetriamine (3.34 g, 32.37 mmol) and carbon tetrachloride (4.98 g, 32.38 mmol) in 100 mL butanol as described earlier³. A mixture of nickel hydroxide (3.00 g, 32.35 mmol) and triethylenetetramine (4.73 g, 32.34 mmol) stirred for 5 min in 100 mL butanol was gradually added to the $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4$ solution with constant stirring. The resulting mixture containing a light green precipitate was refluxed for 1 h and 30 min during which the light green precipitate disappeared, and the mixture turned dark brown. It was then cooled, mixed with 100 mL of water, stirred for 5 min and filtered. A small amount of dirty green residue, was removed and the aqueous dark brownish-red solution was separated from the non-aqueous red solution. It was then concentrated to 20 mL and allowed to stand at room temperature for 7 days to yield a paste-

type bluish-red solid. Some reddish-brown sticky material associated with the product as impurity was removed by benzene/ether (1 : 1) mixture as described in many systems². The dry solid product was dissolved in 100 mL methanol. Concentration of the solution to half volume yielded pink precipitate of the product. The product was filtered, and the brownish-red filtrate was rejected. The pink macrocyclic complex $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{TDSH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{10}]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was finally washed with diethyl ether and dried, yield 3.66 g.

Synthesis of the copper(II) complex of 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,20,23,26,29,30,33,36-tetradecaazadispiro[10.7.10.7]hexatriacontane (TDSH) :

A mixture of diethylenetriamine (4.23 g, 41.00 mmol), carbon tetrachloride (6.31 g, 41.02 mmol) and copper hydroxide (4.00 g, 41.00 mmol) in 160 mL butanol was stirred and refluxed for 8 h to yield a bluish-green solution of the macrocyclic product $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{HTCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_4$ as described in the literature². A mixture of copper hydroxide (4.00 g, 41.00 mmol) and triethylenetetramine was added to the above

Table 1. Analytical and physical data for the macrocyclic compounds

Compd.	Colour (Colour at D.p.)	Yield (%) (M.p. °C)	Λ_M ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)
				C	H	N	Ni/Cu	Cl ^c	
[Ni ₄ (TDSH)(H ₂ O) ₁₀]Cl ₈ ·5H ₂ O C ₂₂ H ₈₄ Cl ₈ N ₁₄ Ni ₄ O ₁₅	Pink (Light brown/ black) ^a	17.36 (250)	811	20.20 (20.57)	6.50 (6.51)	14.99 (15.05)	18.07 (18.01)	21.68 (21.75)	– (1303.6)
[Cu ₄ (TDSH)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₈ ·5H ₂ O C ₂₂ H ₅₈ Cl ₈ Cu ₄ N ₁₄ O ₂	Blue (Brown)	8.07 (180) ^d	820	24.36 (24.27)	5.37 (5.38)	18.06 (18.02)	23.31 (23.35)	25.97 (26.05)	1088.0 (1088.7)
TDSH·14HCl C ₂₂ H ₆₈ Cl ₁₄ N ₁₄	Cream –	91.31 (158)	–	25.85 (25.77)	6.27 (6.70)	19.12 (19.13)	–	48.56 (48.40)	1024.0 (1025.3)
[Ni ₃ (DDCO)(H ₂ O) ₈]Cl ₆ C ₁₈ H ₅₈ Cl ₈ N ₁₀ Ni ₃ O ₈	Violet (Black)	– (248) ^d	627	21.48 (21.56)	5.82 (5.84)	13.92 (13.97)	17.50 (17.57)	21.16 (21.22)	– (1002.6)
[Ni ₄ (TTCO)(H ₂ O) ₁₀]Cl ₈ C ₂₄ H ₇₈ Cl ₈ N ₁₄ Ni ₄ O ₁₀	Pink (Black) ^b	– (236) ^d	964	23.26 (23.22)	6.34 (6.35)	15.78 (15.80)	18.96 (18.91)	22.78 (22.84)	– (1241.6)

^aLight brown liquid at 280 °C, black solid at 300 °C; ^bBlack at 275 °C; ^cIonizable chloride ion; ^dDecomposition.

solution and the content was further heated to reflux at 117 °C for 3 h and 30 min to yield a green mixture. The resulting mixture was then cooled and stirred for 10 min with 100 mL of water and filtered. The brown residue and the non-aqueous brown layer of the filtrate were rejected as in other systems. Blackish-brown aqueous layer of the filtrate was dried to yield a sticky mass. The sticky mass was treated with benzene/ether (1 : 1) mixture on a filter paper as described earlier. The filter paper absorbed blackish-green impurity leaving behind blue crystals of the product. Crystals of [Cu₄(TDSH)(H₂O)₂]Cl₈ were further washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure, yield 1.8 g.

Synthesis of nickel(II) complexes of 2,5,8,11,14,17,19,22,25,28-decaza-9,10-dichlorobicyclo-[16.10.0]octacosane (DDCO) and 2,5,8,10,13,16,19,21,24,27,29,32,35,38-tetradecaazatricyclo-[26.10.0.0^{9,20}]octatriacontane (TTCO) :

A mixture containing nickel hydroxide (3.00 g, 32.35 mmol), diethylenetriamine (3.34 g, 32.37 mmol) and 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane (5.43 g, 32.35 mmol) in 120 mL butanol was heated to reflux for 2 h. The complex of nickel(II) with the macrocyclic ligand HTCO thus formed in solution³ was allowed to react further with triethylenetetramine (4.73 g, 32.34 mmol) and nickel hydroxide (3.00 g, 32.35 mmol). The resulting new mixture containing a green precipitate was refluxed for 3 h. The green precipitate disappeared after 1 h of

heating. Finally, a deep violet solution along with a violet precipitate was obtained. The mixture was cooled at 20 °C and stirred with 80 mL of water. The light violet aqueous solution of the product, which was separated from the green residue and the non-aqueous colourless solution yielded sticky violet crystals after concentration to 20 mL and then refrigerated below 5 °C. After benzene/ether (1 : 1) treatment, the product was further dissolved in minimum amount of water, concentrated and allowed to stand at room temperature. After 15 days, a mixture of violet crystals and a pink paste was obtained. 50 mL of methanol was added to the mixture with constant shaking. A light pink product, [Ni₄(TTCO)(H₂O)₁₀]Cl₈, floating on top was separated from the heavy violet crystals of the other product, [Ni₃(DDCO)(H₂O)₈]Cl₆ by decantation. The violet crystals are slightly soluble in methanol and were purified by washing with acetone and dried, yield 2.62 g. The solution containing the pink precipitate was filtered. The filtrate containing impurities is violet due to the solubility of the violet crystals and, hence was rejected. Washing of the pink precipitate with methanol followed by acetone in which it is insoluble, yielded a pure pink powder, yield 2.46 g.

A sample of 4.23 g (41.00 mmol) diethylenetriamine was allowed to condense with 6.88 g (41.00 mmol) of 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane in the presence of 4.00 g (41.00 mmol) copper hydroxide to yield the Cu-HTCO complex. The blue reaction mixture in 150 mL butanol

Fig. 2. Suggested structures of the nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of TDSH.

was refluxed for 8 h as described earlier². Another stirred mixture of copper hydroxide (4.00 g, 41.00 mmol) and triethylenetetramine (6.00 g, 41.03 mmol) in 100 mL of butanol was then added to the above mixture with constant stirring. It was refluxed for 3 h and 30 min during which the mixture changed from blue to dark blue. After stirring the mixture with 100 mL of water the brownish-black residue, non-aqueous light blue layer and the aqueous deep blue layer were separated as usual. However, concentration and refrigeration of the aqueous solution did not yield the macrocyclic product.

Preparation of 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,20,23,26,29,30,33,36-tetradecaazadispiro[10.7.10.7]hexatriacontane hydrochloride (TDSH.14HCl) :

1.0 g (0.92 mmol) $[Cu_4(TDSH)(H_2O)_2]Cl_8$ was dissolved in 100 mL water. The solution was acidified

with 5 mL conc. HCl (12 N), then H_2S gas was passed into it for about 15 min, and the resulting black precipitate was removed by filtration. Removal of copper was checked by passing H_2S again into the filtrate. The metal ion-free, colourless filtrate was concentrated to 20 mL and kept for crystallization for 15 days at room temperature. The resulting cream-coloured, fine crystals of TDSH.14HCl were washed with diethyl ether and dried under reduced pressure, yield 0.86 g.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The hexaaza ligand 1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaaza-8,8,16,16-tetrachlorocyclohexadecane (HTCH) or 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclooctadecane (HTCO) is generated by condensation

Fig. 3. Suggested structures of the nickel(II) complexes of TTCO and DDCO.

of two molecules of diethylenetriamine with two molecules of carbon tetrachloride or 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane respectively, in presence of nickel hydroxide or copper hydroxide^{2,3}. The four Cl-atoms of HTCH or HTCO are responsible for an increase in the ring number of the macrocycle. The template condensation of triethylenetetramine with the Ni^{II} complex of HTCH, Ni^{II} complex of HTCO or Cu^{II} complex of HTCH in the presence of the corresponding metal hydroxide in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio (complex : amine : metal hydroxide) yields new metal complexes. The macrocyclic ligands 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,20,23,26, 29,30,33,36-tetradecaazadispiro[10.7.10.7]hexatriacontane (TDSH) and 2,5,8,10,13,16,19,21,24,27, 29,32,35,38-tetradecaazatricyclo[20.10.0.0^{9,20}]octatriacontane (TTCO) or 2,5,8,11,14,17,19,22,25, 28-decaaza-9,10-dichlorobicyclo[16.10.0]octacosane (DDCO) are generated from the HTCH and HTCO systems, respectively. Initially, metal hydroxide coordinates with triethylenetetramine and then condensation takes place between the metal tetramine complex and metal complexes of HTCH or HTCO.

All the complexes were characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, conductivity measurements, mass spectra, infrared and proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectral studies. The results of elemental analyses reported in Table 1 indicate the stoichiometry which is in agreement with the formulation given. Evidence for cyclization is demonstrated by the absence of infrared absorption bands that may be attributed to either free or coordinated NH₂ groups^{4,6-8}.

Infrared spectra :

TDSH system : The infrared spectrum of $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{TDSH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{10}]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicates the absence of bands due to NH_2 groups. A medium but very sharp band attributed to a secondary amine appears at 3150 cm^{-1} . This suggests the presence of a completely condensed macrocyclic organic ligand. The N–H bending mode is also seen as medium intensity band at 1592 cm^{-1} . A weak band at 1160 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the $\nu(\text{C–N})$ vibration. Vibrations for C–H asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring are seen at 2920 , 2870 and 1460 cm^{-1} , respectively. A shoulder at 436 cm^{-1} is attributed to the metal-nitrogen bond. Coordination of water is supported by the presence of a very strong but very sharp band at 3220 cm^{-1} followed by either weak or very weak bands at 1640 , 760 , 600 and 570 cm^{-1} , assigned to stretching, bending, rocking, wagging and twisting vibrations of the water molecule, respectively. A weak but very sharp band at 540 cm^{-1} is attributed to the $\nu(\text{Ni–O})$ vibrations.

The N–H stretching mode of the secondary amine in the infrared spectrum of copper complex of TDSH is seen at 3132 cm^{-1} , while the position of the $\delta(\text{N–H})$ vibration is at 1587 cm^{-1} . A weak band at 1140 cm^{-1} is associated with $\nu(\text{C–N})$. Coordination of the ligand through nitrogen is evidenced by a very weak band at 543 cm^{-1} . The bands for coordinated water are seen at 3236 , 1659 , 765 , 621 and 525 cm^{-1} and are attributed to $\nu(\text{O–H})$, $\delta(\text{O–H})$, rocking, wagging and $\nu(\text{Cu–O})$ vibrations, respectively^{9,10}.

The presence of bands attributed to $\nu(\text{N–H})$ modes of secondary amine in the ligand hydrochloride is in agreement with that of its nickel or copper complex. A medium but sharp band for $\delta(\text{N–H})$ is seen at 1588 cm^{-1} . The bands assigned to C–H asymmetric, symmetric stretching, scissoring and $\nu(\text{C–N})$ appear at 2946 , 2884 , 1450 and 445 cm^{-1} , respectively.

DDCO system :

The infrared spectrum of the nickel complex of DDCO exhibits very sharp bands at the frequencies 2900 (strong), 2850 (medium) and 1440 cm^{-1} (strong) due to C–H asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring vibrations, respectively. Coordination of water is supported by the presence of a very strong but broad band in the $3420\text{--}3250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region ($\nu(\text{O–H})$ mode) followed by bands at 648 , 610 and 565 cm^{-1}

Table 2. Important IR bands of the macrocyclic compounds

Compd.	IR bands (cm^{-1}) ^a
$[\text{Ni}_4(\text{TDSH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{10}]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3220 (vs,vsp), 3150 (m,vsp), 2920 (s), 2870 (vw,sp), 2100 (m,sp), 1640 (w,vsp), 1592 (m,vsp), 1460 (m,sp), 1398 (m,vsp), 1380 (w,vsp), 1280 (w,sp), 1240 (vw,sp), 1200 (vw), 1180 (w,vsp), 1160 (vw), 1120 (m,sp), 1060 (s), 1000 (vw,sp), 962 (vs,vsp), 890 (w,vsp), 790 (vw,sp), 760 (vv,vsp), 670 (s), 600 (vw), 570 (w,vsp), 540 (w,vsp), 508 (vw,vsp), 470 (m,vsp), 436 (sh), 366 (vw), 315(vw)
$[\text{Cu}_4(\text{TDSH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_8$	3236 (s,sp), 3132 (w,vsp), 2945 (w,vsp), 2883 (w,vsp), 2735 (vw), 2333 (w,sp), 2125 (vw), 1659 (w), 1587 (m,vsp), 1448 (m,sp), 1387 (m,vsp), 1319 (vw), 1256 (w,sp), 1140 (w), 1088 (s,vsp), 1028 (m,vsp), 988 (w), 910 (sh), 837 (vw), 765 (w), 691 (w), 621 (w,sp), 525 (w,sp), 453 (vw)
TDSH.14HCl	3155 (w,sp), 2946 (m), 2884 (m), 1585 (m,sp), 1570 (vw), 1450 (vw,sp), 1375 (m,sp), 1214 (vw), 1145 (w,vsp), 1050 (vw), 982 (m,sp), 840 (vw), 760 (w,sp), 540 (vw)
$[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DDCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\text{Cl}_6$	3420–3250 (vs,b), 3150 (vs,sp), 2900 (s,vsp), 2850 (m,vsp), 2100 (m, sp), 1640 (m, vsp), 1560 (v,vsp), 1465 (m,sp), 1440 (s,vsp), 1378 (m,vsp), 1310 (s,sp), 1268 (m,vsp), 1240 (m,vsp), 1078 (vs,sp), 1044 (vw,vsp), 1000 (vs,vsp), 980 (vs,vsp), 930 (s,vsp), 900 (vw,vsp), 880 (s,vsp), 810 (w,vsp), 648 (w,vsp), 611 (s,vsp), 565 (m,sp), 515 (vw,sp), 480 (vw), 398 (m,vsp), 375 (w,vsp)
$[\text{Ni}_4(\text{TTCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{10}]\text{Cl}_8$	3350–3227 (vs,b), 3161 (w,vsp), 2932 (m,vsp), 2878 (m,vsp), 2112 (m,vsp), 1645 (m,vsp), 1595 (m,vsp), 1466 (m,sp), 1382 (m,vsp), 1333 (m,vsp), 1284 (w,vsp), 1253 (vw), 1192 (vw,sp), 1126 (m,vsp), 1012 (s,sp), 974 (vs,vsp), 895 (m,vsp), 860 (vw), 770 (vw), 677 (s,vsp), 574 (m,vsp), 543 (m,vsp), 476 (m,vsp), 446 (vw), 409 (vw)

^aAbbreviations used : b = broad, d = doublet, m = medium, s = strong, sh = shoulder, sp = sharp, vb = very broad, vs = very strong, vsp = very sharp, vw = very weak, w = weak.

assigned to the rocking, wagging and twisting vibrations of water molecules. A very weak but sharp band at 515 cm^{-1} is attributed to the $\nu(\text{Ni–O})$ vibration of coordinated water. Bonding of the metal to the macrocycle through nitrogen is confirmed by the appearance of a very weak intensity band at 480 cm^{-1} .

The N–H mode of secondary amine groups is seen as a single band at 3150 cm^{-1} . The N–H bending peak appears at 1560 cm^{-1} .

TTCO system : In the infrared spectrum of nickel complex of TTCO bands attributed to functional groups are observed at 2932, 2878 and 1466 cm^{-1} (C–H asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring, respectively), 1126 cm^{-1} (C–N, stretching), 3161 cm^{-1} (N–H, stretching) and 1595 cm^{-1} (N–H, bending). The presence of coordinated water molecule is indicated by the bands at 3350–3227 (very strong, broad), 1645 (medium, very strong), 770 (very weak), 677 (strong, very sharp), 574 (medium, very sharp) and 543 cm^{-1} (medium, very sharp), assigned to $\nu(\text{O–H})$, $\delta(\text{O–H})$, rocking, wagging, twisting and $\nu(\text{Ni–O})$ vibrations, respectively.

Comparison of TDSH, DDCO and TTCO systems :

As expected the greater complexing tendency of TDSH with copper than nickel is indicated by the metal-nitrogen stretching vibration frequencies ($\nu(\text{Cu–N})$ 543 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{Ni–N})$ 436 cm^{-1}). The lower $\nu(\text{N–H})$ or $\nu(\text{C–N})$ vibration frequency in the copper complex (Fig. 2) also favour stronger copper-ligand coordination. The stretching vibration frequency order : $\text{Ni–O} > \text{Cu–O}$ is probably because of lower electron density on the ligand coordinated to nickel. In the complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) with TDSH and HTCH (the HTCH-nickel complex³ and HTCH-copper complex² reported earlier) the Cu–N or Ni–N bond order follows the trend : $\text{TDSH} > \text{HTCH}$. The stronger coordinating behaviour of TDSH (obtained by condensation of HTCH and triethylenetetramine) is probably associated with the presence of two additional [11]- N_4 rings and the absence of electron withdrawing four Cl-atoms.

The complexes $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DDCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\text{Cl}_6$ and $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{TTCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{10}]\text{Cl}_6$ (Fig. 3) have been prepared by condensation of $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4$ and triethylenetetramine. The nickel-nitrogen bond density increases in the nickel complexes of TTCO or DDCO as compared to that in the nickel complex of HTCO, may be expected because of a decrease in the number or absence of electron-withdrawing Cl atoms and the presence of additional [12]- N_4 ring(s). The $\nu(\text{Ni–N})$ vibration energy order in the nickel complex of TDSH and the nickel complex of TTCO is $\text{TTCO} > \text{TDSH}$, which shows that probably four nickel(II) ions in the larger cavities of TTCO are more comfortably fitted than in the TDSH cavities.

¹H NMR spectra :

A broad singlet at 4.68 ppm in the Ni complex of TTCO may be assigned to the NH-proton resonance. Slightly upfield from the NH resonances complex multiplets in the region 3.23–2.85 ppm are ascribed to the methylene protons. The coordinated water resonances in the complex are probably obscured by the NH or CH_2 signals.

Mass spectra :

Determination of molecular weights of $\text{TDSH} \cdot 14\text{HCl}$ and $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{TDSH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_8$ by FABMS has been very useful in completing their characterization. The highest mass peak found in the spectrum occur at m/z values close to their molecular ion (Table 1) and are very weak and are comparable to those observed in earlier reported aza macrocyclic complexes^{4,8}.

Solubility, conductivity and other data :

All of the compounds are highly soluble in water and generally in polar solvents like ethanol, methanol, DMF, DMSO, etc. The molecular conductivity of the complexes and the number of ionizable chloride ions in all the macrocyclic molecules recorded in Table 1 are in support of their ionic structures. The molar conductance value $627\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$ determined for the nickel complex of DDCO, is consistent with a 6 : 1 electrolyte. The nickel complex of TDSH, copper complex of TDSH and nickel complex of TTCO are 8 : 1 electrolytes. Five water molecules are lost from the nickel or copper complexes of TDSH on heating at $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. These water molecules correspond to the water of crystallization in the complexes. But, no water molecule is liberated from the nickel complexes of DDCO and TTCO below $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All molecules are coordinated to the nickel ion. The macrocyclic compounds including the ligand hydrochloride are thermally stable. The nickel complexes of TDSH and TTCO melt at 250 and $236\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and decompose at 280 and $257\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. The melting point of $\text{TDSH} \cdot 14\text{HCl}$ is comparatively low ($158\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The copper complex of TDSH and the nickel complex of DDCO decompose at 180 and $248\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively.

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